

The New Technological Order: Why the Automotive Lifecycle Must Evolve

Addressing the complexity crisis, skill gaps, and the human factor through a new paradigm of product-consumer interaction.

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The classic modern model of a car's life cycle involves manufacturing and assembly using labor and production facilities of varying degrees of automation or robotization at a factory by a single company. The car is then sold through a dealer network by another company, serviced and repaired with the help of labor and production facilities by other companies. And at the end of the life cycle, they end up for recycling, where labor and means of production are used again.

Every year, the technical complexity and information density of the car increases, both for production and for maintenance. The change of the model range and platforms is becoming more frequent. Production and service experience does not have time to accumulate, the number of errors increases, and the quality of service decreases. The staff of the services cannot keep up with the information flows and **the problem of the shortage of qualified personnel will only increase.** The client does not receive the expected service, repair timeframes, and cost, and subsequently switches to another brand of car.

Due to increasingly stringent environmental requirements, **vehicle recycling technology will be revised** and transformed into a process comparable to manufacturing, where information support (and therefore the availability of qualified personnel) will play a significant role. **All these identified problems and many others will have to be solved in the foreseeable future in order not to lose out in the competition.**

And, as can be seen from the description of the problems, **the constant increase in the information flow is fundamental. And the introduction of AI systems into all processes of the car's life cycle will be inevitable.**

The figure shows a diagram of the introduction of AI into technological processes, production, service and recycling of a car.

This scheme will partially redirect the information flows and relieve the person, but it will not solve other problems. A person still remains an intermediary between the information array, the AI system, the means of production and the car. Each person interprets information in their own way, and on the way from the information array to the target destination (car), information is lost and

distorted. **The human factor, in the context of physical limitations, errors and abuses, affects the outcome of production and service work.** The organization of control at different levels, augmented reality AI systems, anthropomorphic robots and other innovations will never solve this problem completely. And this problem imposes **many limitations on the system in its development and application. It is necessary to review the very concept of the product (car) life cycle.**

And this new concept of technological processes of the product life cycle (car) can be designated as a **Model Without Human Intervention (MWHI)**. The fundamental **principle of the new model is the withdrawal of the human factor beyond the contour of the product (car) — the buyer.**

The diagram of the MWHI model is shown in the figure :

It should be noted that the introduction of **MWHI will require significant changes and adaptations of the vehicle design.** There is no direct human involvement in the entire production-sale-service-disposal chain . It will be replaced by an AI-controlled MWHI technology complex. Human functions will be redirected to servicing the MWHI complex itself. What are the advantages of this concept:

- the absence of abuses and errors caused by the human factor, a significant reduction in the costs associated with hiring staff
- the information flow runs through the entire product lifecycle chain without changes or losses
- **a significant decrease in the number of workers**, including highly skilled ones .MWHI maintenance will require significantly fewer personnel than in the classic model. The accumulation and application of experience by the staff is more stable
- increasing the quality and stability of products and services for the end user
- **the same quality of products and service for all consumers**
- **the possibility of increasing the complexity of production, service, disposal without loss of quality and in a short time**
- **high scalability** across the entire product lifecycle chain
- optimization of logistics, production and service workload
- **deep implementation of AI systems in the technological process**
- **the ability to concentrate the entire product lifecycle in one hand (company). Distribution of profits between production, service, and disposal depending on market conditions. Increase the flexibility of business processes and competitiveness.**
- the business model is becoming more stable and predictable .

The next section of the article will discuss the design features of the MWHI concept vehicle and the MWHI modules used in production, service, and recycling.